

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

A REVIEW ON IMMEDIATE RELEASE DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM

M. Sowjanya^{*}, S. Pavani

Joginpally B.R. Pharmacy College Yenkapally, Moinabad-500075, Hyderabad Telangana.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 11/04/2024

Available online

30/06/2024

Keywords

Croscarmellose,
Sodium Starch Glycolate,
and Crospovidone.

ABSTRACT

Tablets are the most popular of all dosage forms in existence because they are convenient, self-administered, compact and easy to prepare. However in many cases immediate treatment initiation is required compared to conventional treatments, immediate release tablet formulations are those using superdisintegrants such as croscarmellose, sodium starch glycolate, and crospovidone. These superdisintegrants cause tablets to disintegrate quickly after intragastric administration. Despite the remarkable advances in drug delivery, the oral route remains the most preferred route for the delivery of therapeutic agents due to low treatment costs and ease of administration, resulting in high level of patient compliance. Tablets is that do not require water and dissolve or disintegrate rapidly in saliva within seconds. Due to action of super solubilizers in the formulation or other new manufacturing technique. The demand of oral disintegrating tablets is high compared to other oral dosage forms {tablets, capsules, dry syrup chewing gums etc. Especially among elderly and paediatric patients travellers indigestion, patient and psychiatric patients. Patients considering the benefits of immediate release tablet and their growing demand. Various excipients are used in the preparation of tablet such as microcrystal, cellulose, lactose etc. Immediate release liquids and parenteral dosage forms are also used in treatment. These advances in the immediate release system also provide opportunities to increase the market and other types of drugs {such as neuroleptics cardiovascular drug analgesics antihistamine etc}. can be considered as competitors for this form of immediate release. These immediate release tablets and preparation technique, and dosage form evaluations.

Corresponding author

M. Sowjanya Lakshmi

Assistant Professor

M.Pharmacy (Pharmaceutics)

Joginpally B.R. Pharmacy College Yenkapally,

Moinabad-500075, Hyderabad Telangana.

7382870710

sainymil@gmail.com

Please cite this article in press as **M. Sowjanya Lakshmi et al.** A Review on Immediate Release Drug Delivery System. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2024;14(06).

Copy right © 2024 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

INTRODUCTION

Immediate drug release system are described as immediate release tablets prepared to dissolve and release the drug without the need for special rate control feature such as special coating or alternatives technologies, and therefore it is also a drug delivery system. The oral route is the most convenient and commonly used for drug administration (6,7). Oral, administration is the most common method of systemic action due to ease of ingestion avoidance of pain, versatility, and most importantly, patient compliance suitability for industrial production and improved stability and bioavailability. In an increasingly populous nation such as India, the demand for medical services is also increasing due to changing lifestyles and called "fast culture" health status is hardly considered anymore. Achieving health as defined by the world health organisation is difficult in this incredible pace of life. Efficient management of diseases and disorders is the ultimate objective of any delivery system. Minimal side effects and increased patient compliance in a cost effective manner. Multiple oral disintegrating tablet technologies based on direct compression. Pharmaceutical formulation include all compound in which the rate of release of the drug from the formulation is at least 70% of the active ingredient within 4 hours, such as within 3 hours, preferably within 2 hours, particularly preferably within 1.5 hours, especially within 1 hour include formulation after administration. (1, 2, 3, 4)

Advantages of immediate release drug delivery system

- Rapid initiation of action.
- Suitable for industrial production.
- Improved stability and bioavailability
- Can be adapted and modified to existing processing and packaging machinery.

Problems with existing oral dosage form :(9, 10,11)

- Patients may suffer from tremors which make it difficult to ingest powders or noliuids. In

Dysphagia, physical obstruction or adhesions in the esophagus can lead to gastrointestinal Ulcers.

- Product cost is the main factors as parenteral formulations are the most expensive and unpleasant.
- Patients are instructed to use buccal and sublingual preparations as they can cause irritation of the oral mucosa

Conventional techniques for producing immediate release tablets includes

1. Tablet Moulding
2. Direct Compression
3. Wet Granulation

Tablet Moulding:

This technology was water soluble ingredient, so the tablets disintegrates and dissolve quickly. The powder mixture is moistened with a hydroalcoholic solvent and formed into tablet using lower compression pressures than traditional tablet compression. The solvent is then removed by air drying. molded tablets have a porous structure that improves solubility. Two common problems are poor mechanical strength and taste masking properties. Binders such as sucrose, acacia wood, and polyvinylpyrrolidone can increase the mechanical strength of tablets. (12)

Direct compression: (13, 9, 14)

In this method, tablets are compressed directly from the drug and excipient mixture without any prior processing. The mixture to be compacted must have sufficient flow properties and be cohesive under pressure to allow pre-treatment such as wet granulation. Only a few drugs are required and can be compressed directly into tablets of acceptable quality. The type of explosive and its proportions are of paramount importance. Other factor considered include particle size, distribution, tablet hardness, and water absorption capacity Wet granulation: (15, 16)

Wet granulation

This method uses a liquid binder to slightly agglomerate the powder mixture. The amount of liquid must be properly controlled, because, too much moisture will make granule too hard, and too much moisture will make the granule too hard, too low moisture will the granule too soft and brittle.

Procedure:

- Weigh and mix the active ingredient and excipients.
 - Wet granule are prepared by adding liquid binders and adhesives to the powder mixtures and mixing thoroughly.
 - Shift the wet mass to form pallets or granules.
 - For drying conventional tray dryers or fluidized bed dryers are suitable.
- After the granules are dry, pass them through a smaller sieve then the one used for wet mass to produce the granules of uniform size.

Excipients used in immediate release drug delivery system: (9,10,17,11,18)

Excipient balances the properties of the active ingredient in an immediate release dosage form. This requires a thorough understanding of the chemistry of these excipients and clarity from formulators to prevent interactions with the active ingredient and determine the cost of these ingredients. The role of excipients plays an important role in the formulation of fast releasing tablets.

Super disintegrants: (10, 14)

A disintegrant is an excipient added to a tablet or capsule mixture to help breakup the compressed mass when placed in a liquid environment.

Advantages:

Effective at low concentration.

Less impact on compressibility and fluidity Highly effective within the grain.

Commonly used superdisintegrants: (1)

Commonly used super disintegrants includes

1}.sodium starch glycolate: used in concentration of 2-8% optimal concentration 4%.

2}. microcrystalline cellulose: use at a concentration of 2-5% of tablet weight.

3}. cross linked povidone: use at a concentration of 2-5% of tablet weight.

4}.low substituted hydroxyl propyl cellulose: insoluble in water.LH-11 and LH-21 swell quickly in water and have the highest degree of swelling. Certain grades also provide some bonding properties while maintaining damping capacity. Recommended concentration: 1-5%

Ideal properties of super disintegrants:

1}.a rapid decay should occur

2}.must has good shape and flow properties.

3}.It should have good particle size, hydration capacity and compressibility.

4}.must has low water solubility.

5}.the aim to create a compact, non-friable tablet

Evaluation of powder mixtures: (3)

The prepared mixtures are evaluated by the following tests:

1] Angle of repose

2] Bulk density

3] Tapped density

4) Carr's compressibility index.

Angle of repose:

Angle of repose was determined using the fixed funnel method. The fixed funnel methods uses a funnel with its tip fixed at a fixed height [2cm] above a piece of graph paper placed on a flat horizontal surface,and the granule or tablet mixture is poured into the funnel with a tip oHf the conical mound just touching the surface. Pour gently through the funnel until the where r' is the radius of the base of the conical pile. The angle of repose was calculated using the following formula.

$$\Theta = \tan^{-1} (h/r)$$

Here h=height of pile

R=radius of pile

Θ=angle of repose

Bulk density (17)

The bulk density apparatus was utilised to measure the bulk density by filling the granules into a graduated Cylinder. The granules' mass (m) and bulk volume (Vb) were calculated. The following formula was used to determine the bulk density.

$$eb = m / Vb$$

TAPPED DENSITY

In the bulk density device, the measurement cylinder containing a known mass of granule blend was tapped 1000 times over a predetermined period of time.Measurements were made of the mass of the granules (m) and the minimal volume the cylinder (Vt) could hold. The following formula was used to get the tapped density.

$$et = m/Vt (4)$$

Carr's index, or compressibility index :-(18)

Compressibility Index, often known as Carr's Index [24]

The compressibility index dictates the features of the flow properties of the granules that Carr developed. By examining the granules' percentage compressibility, one can directly calculate the potential powder arch and stability. The Carr's index can be found using the following formula.

Carr's index is $(100 - \frac{e_b}{e_t}) \times 100$ (5), where e_t is the tapped density and e_b is the bulk density of the granules.

Hausner's ratio

The Hausner's ratio is used to determine the granule flow.

POST COMPRESSION PARAMETERS (19)

A Vernier calliper is used to measure the thickness of each tablet. Typically, mm is used as the measurement unit for thickness. Every tablet has a maximum thickness deviation of 5%.

Hardness (20)

A tablet's hardness is related to how resistant it is to attrition and fracture as a solid specimen. The Monsanto hardness tester can be used to measure tablet hardness, which is expressed in kg/cm².

Friability (21)

The Roche friabilator was used to determine the tablet's friability. This apparatus rotates at 25 rpm, falling a tablet six inches in height with each revolution, subjecting the tablet to the combined effects of shock and abrasion. A pre-weighed sample of tablets was spun through 100 revolutions in the friabilator. Tablets were reweighed after being dusted with a gentle cotton towel.

The formula yields the % friability (% F).

$$\frac{\text{Starting mass} - \text{Ending weight}}{\text{Starting mass}} \times 100 = \% \text{ Friability}$$

Starting mass $\times 100$

Whereas, the pills' initial weight before weight) and following the test (final weight)

Correspondingly.

Variation in Weight (26)

Using a Shimadzu digital scale, 20 tablets were individually weighed for the weight variation test. The average weight of each tablet was then determined, and the weights of each tablet were compared to the average. After calculating the % weight deviation, the results were compared to the USP requirements.

Test for disintegration [22]

Disintegration test equipment was used to measure the disintegration time. Every tube in the basket held one tablet. The basket was submerged in water at $37 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, with the bottom surface composed of a stainless-steel screen (mesh no. 10). A stop watch was used to measure the amount of time needed for the tablet to completely dissolve in each tube. Dispersible tablets must dissolve in 3 minutes when tested with the tablet disintegration test in order to meet pharmacological criteria. Studies on in vitro dissolution (25)

All of the manufactured tablets were subjected to in vitro dissolving tests using the USP paddle method at 100 rpm in 900 ml of pH 1.2 HCl buffer as the dissolution media, which was kept at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. At the designated intervals, a 5 ml aliquot was taken out and filtered using Whatman filter paper. After each sampling, an equal volume of fresh medium that had been pre-warmed to 37°C was added to the dissolution media to keep the volume constant for the duration of the test. After that, the samples are examined spectrophotometrically at 210 nm to determine the absorbance.

For three months, stability chambers (Thermo Lab Scientific Equipment Pvt.Ltd., Mumbai, India) were kept at $40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}/75 \pm 5\%$ RH. Periodically, the tablets were taken out and examined for physical attributes, pharmacological content.

Studies on stability (23)

In accordance with the recommendations of ICH (The International Conference of Harmonisation), the formulation was put through expedited stability testing. For three months, the tablets, which were packed in airtight containers, were kept at $40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}/75 \pm 5\%$ RH in stability chambers provided by Thermo Lab Scientific Equipment Pvt. Ltd. in Mumbai, India. Periodically, the tablets were taken out and examined for physical attributes, drug composition, in vitro drug release, and other factors. The tablets were visually inspected every week to check for any physical changes and variations in the amount of medication.

WETTING TIME (24)

A straightforward technique can be used to determine the tablets' wetting time. A petri dish with a diameter of 10 cm is filled with five round tissue papers. Petridish is infused with a water-soluble colour called eosin. On the tissue paper's surface, a tablet is gently inserted. Wetting time is defined as the amount of time needed for water to reach the tablet's upper surface. A tablet was introduced to 10 millilitres of phosphate buffer solution (pH 6.8) at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ for the in vitro dispersion period [32]. The amount of time needed for a pill to completely disperse was calculated.

CONCLUSION

This market area presents a clear possibility for the introduction of new improved oral solutions. Approximately one third of patients require a drug to take effect quickly. As a result, they often do not comply with traditional medication therapy. Which lowers the effectiveness of treatment as a whole. The majority of patients require medication with a quick therapeutic effect, these dose forms provide a quick onset of action. These instant release tablets are more advantageous than other dosage forms and have strong patient compliance. A novel dosage form known as the quick release pharmaceutical form has been

Created, providing the benefits of convenience and simplicity of dosing together. The medication will release from these pills at the fastest rate than before. Owing to the previously mentioned limitation of existing technologies, there exists an unfulfilled demand for enhanced manufacturing procedures for pharmaceuticals in immediate release form that are robust mechanically, facilitate effortless handling and packaging, and have production expenses similar to those of traditional formulations. Formulators have worked very hard to create a novel kind of tablet dosage form for oral administration that dissolves and disintegrates quickly with increased solubility in order to meet their medical needs. A prolongation of market exclusivity such as that offered by a dose form with instant release results in increased revenue, as well as concentrating on the patient demographic of underserved and undertreated.

REFERENCES

1. Asief Shaik, R. Aruna, A. M. S. Sudhakar Babu, P. Venkateswara Rao. A review on immediate release drug delivery system. International Journal of Research in Pharmaceutical and Nano Sciences.
2. Chetana A. Padekar*, Dr. Makarand G. Gambhire. A review on immediate release tablets. International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Application, Volume 6, Issue 3, May-June 2021, pp 1197-1205.
3. Manish Jaimini, Sonamranga, Amitkumarsanjaykumarsharma, Bhupendrasinghchauhan. A review on immediate release drug delivery system by using design of experiment. Journal of Drug Discovery and Therapeutics 1(12) 2013, 21-27.
4. Nyolsandeep*, Dr. M. M. Gupta. A review on immediate drug release dosage form. Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics 2013, 3(2), 155-161.
5. Debjit Bhowmik*, Amrendrasingh, Darshgautam, P. Samathkumar. A review on immediate release drug delivery system - A novel drug delivery system. Journal of Pharmaceutics and Biological Sciences, Issue 2320-1924.
6. Nyol S., Gupta M. Immediate drug release dosage form: a review. Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics, 2013; 3(2):155-161.
7. Patel K., Vyas J., Upadhyay U.. Formulation and evaluation of sustained release matrix tablets of nateglinide. Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics, 2015; 5(5):19-25.
8. Mahboob MBH, Tehseen R, Jamshaid M, Irfan B and Zulfiqar AS: Oral films: a comprehensive review. International Current Pharmaceutical Journal 2016; 5(12): 111-17.
9. Susijit Sahoo, Mishra B, Biswal P I K, Omprakash Panda, Satosh Kumar Mahapatra and Goutam Kumar Jana. Fast Dissolving Tablet: A Potential Drug Delivery System, Drug Invention Today, 2(2), 2010, 130-133.
10. Ustavpatel, Khusbhupatel, Darshan Shan. "A review on immediate release drug delivery system", IJPRBS, 1(5), 2012, 37-66.
11. Gupta A, Mishra A K, Gupta V, Bansal P, Singh R and Singh A K. Review Article, Recent Trends of Fast Dissolving Tablet – An Overview of Formulation Technology, International Journal Of Pharmaceutical and Biological Archives, 1(1), 2010, 1-10.
12. Shiyani B G, Dholakiyal R B, Akbari B V, Lodhiyal D J and Ramani G K. Development And Evaluation of Novel Immediate Release Tablets of Metoclopramide Hcl By Direct Compression Using Treated Gellan Gum As Disintegration-Accelerating Agent, Journal of Pharmacy Research, 2(9), 2009, 1460-1464.
13. Vaishali Kilor, Nidhi Sapkal, Jasmine Awari and Bharti Shewale. Development and Characterization of Enteric-Coated Immediate Release Pellets of Aceclofenac By Extrusion/Spheronization Technique Using Carrageenan As A Pelletizing Agent, AAPS PharmSciTech, 11(1), 2010, 336-343.
14. Ustavpatel, Khusbhupatel, Darshan Shan. "A review on immediate release drug delivery system", IJPRBS, 1(5), 2012, 37-66.
15. Gupta A, Mishra A K, Gupta V, Bansal P, Singh R and Singh A K. Review Article, Recent Trends of Fast Dissolving Tablet – An Overview of Formulation Technology, International Journal Of Pharmaceutical and Biological Archives, 1(1), 2010, 1-10.
16. Shiyani B G, Dholakiyal R B, Akbari B V, Lodhiyal D J and Ramani G K. Development And Evaluation of Novel Immediate Release Tablets of Metoclopramide Hcl By Direct Compression Using Treated Gellan Gum As Disintegration- accelerating agent. Journal of Pharmacy Research 2(9), 2009, 1460-1464.
17. Jon Gabrielsson, Nils-Olof Lindberg and Torbjorn Lundstedt. Multivariate Methods in Pharmaceutical Applications, J. Chromatogr., 16(3), 2002, 141-160.
18. Tanmoy Ghosh, Amitava Ghosh and Devi Prasad. A Review on New Generation Orodispersible Tablets and Its Future Prospective, International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 3(1), 2011, 1-12.
19. Sahoo CK, Mohanty D, Bhaskar J, Ramana DV. Formulation and Evaluation of Fast Dissolving Tablets of Carvedilol using Sodium Starch Glycolate. Int. J. Pharm. Sci. DOI: 10.35629/7781-060311971202 | Impact Factor value 7.429 | ISO 9001: 2008 Certified Journal Page 1202 Rev. Res., 51(1), 2018, 35-40.
20. Ahmed JA. A Review on fast dissolving tablet dosage form. Int. J. of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Research. 2 (3), 2015, 1-17.
21. Sahoo CK, Sahoo NK, Sahu M, Moharana AK, Sarangi DK. Formulation and Evaluation of Orodispersible Tablets of Granisetron Hydrochloride Using Agar as Natural Super Disintegrants. Pharm Methods 7(1), 2016, 17-22.
22. Srinivas P, Mahalaxmi R. Preparation and invitro evaluation of nizatidine fast dissolving tablets. Int. J. Pharmtech Res. 3 (3), 2011, 1688-1692.
23. Sahoo CK, Sahoo TK, Moharana AK. Designing of orodispersible tablet of diethyl carbamazepine citrate for the treatment of filariasis, Inter J Appl Biol Pharm Tech. 2, 2011, 70-74.

23. Sahoo CK, Sahoo NK, Sahu M, Alagarsamy V, Moharana AK, Sarangi DK, Satyanarayana K. Formulation and evaluation of orodispersible tablets of granisetron hydrochloride using platago ovate as natural superdisintegrants, Indonesian J. Pharm. 27(1), 2016, 35-43.
24. Tiwari AK, Shah A, Rajpoot A, Manmohan Singh. Formulation and In-vitro Evaluation of Fast dissolving tablets of Drotaverine HCl. J. Chem. Pharm. Res. 3(4), 2011, 333-341
25. Rai VK, Pathak N, Bhaskar R, Nandi BC, Dey S, Tyagi LK. Optimization of fast dissolving tablet of Raloxifene hydrochloride by wet granulation method. Int J Pharm Sci and drug Res. 1(1), 2009, 51-54.
26. Sahoo CK, Sudhakar M, Bhanja S, Panigrahy UP, Panda KC. Development and evaluation of immediate release tablets of dasatinib using sodium starch glycolate as super disintegrants, Innoriginal International Journal of Sciences 4(1), 2017, 1-4.
27. Sreenivas S.A, Gadad A.P, Patil M.B. Formulation and evaluation of ondasetron hydrochloride directly compressed mouth disintegrating tablets. Indian Drugs, hatt N. Formulation and evaluation of orodispersible taste masked tablets of famotidine. PharmaBiol World 2005; 3: 75-80.
28. Banker G.S, Anderson N. R. In: Lachman L, Lieberman H.A. and Kanig J.L. The Theory and Practice of Industrial Pharmacy. 3rd ed, Mumbai, Varghese Publishing House, 1987, pp 293-399.

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

Convenient online manuscript submission

Access Online first

Double blind peer review policy

International recognition

No space constraints or color figure charges

Immediate publication on acceptance

Inclusion in **ScopeMed** and other full-text repositories

Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com

